

On-organ Sensing Project

Summary of Results

Firstly, thank you again for taking part in the On-organ Sensing project. We greatly appreciate your time and contributions!

Purpose of the study

Many adults have trouble controlling or emptying their bowel. This is a significant global health issue that can profoundly impact daily life, causing distress, embarrassment, anxiety, and pain.

The *On-Organ Sensing* project aimed to develop an innovative system, combining an implantable sensor with a digital interface. The sensor was intended to be attached to the bowel, detect strain changes as stool passed, and transmit this data to the digital interface. The goal was to explore the feasibility and acceptability of this system and how the information it might provide could help adults better understand their intestinal transit (movement of stool) to support improved bowel management and quality of life.

The project was led by Heriot-Watt University, in partnership with Glasgow School of Art, University of Manchester, University of Salford, and University of Stirling. Funded by UK Gov, the research focused on three key areas: Patient perspectives, Sensor engineering, and Digital interface (app) design.

Key findings

Patient perspectives

- Participants noted that they struggled with the lack of predictability of their bowel movements. It was difficult to ascertain if there was a relationship between bowel movements and things like eating/drinking frequency, type or amounts and also with either being sedentary or active and with stress. Overall, this could have an impact on general quality of life, a feeling of low self-worth and isolation.
- There was an optimism that a tool that could give them personalised information about their gut alongside capturing information about their daily activities might allow improved self-management because of the potential to adapt behaviours to suit emerging patterns. There was a belief that this would lead to improved quality of life, increased self efficacy of bowel self-management, reduce reliance on memory and increase engagement with others at work and socially.
- However, participants also felt cautious about the risks that diary recording fatigue might take place, that there could be over-vigilance to the mobile device and anxiety if they forgot their mobile somewhere. There was also a question as to whether they would have confidence in the data that was produced through the device.

Sensor engineering

- The optimum placement for the sensor was identified as the sigmoid colon, which is the last section of the large intestine before the rectum. This allows measurements to be taken with enough warning for the patient.
- The sensor was developed using a range of techniques that have led to a device that has the potential for use either for internal placement or placement on the outside of the large intestine. We have been working with clinicians to try to understand how we focus our work to date in order to ensure we can move our device to the next stages of innovation on this basis. Testing demonstrated that the sensor has the potential to detect intestinal transit, and to do so repeatedly.
- Participants, who had a range of bowel conditions, were generally enthusiastic about the sensor. Nearly all (92%) indicated they would consider having the sensor implanted. However, opinions varied on the preferred implantation method (endoscopic or laparoscopic¹), and some

¹ **Endoscopic procedure:** The sensor would be attached *inside* the colon in an invasive, but non-surgical procedure, similar to a colonoscopy. Patients would need a laxative, sedation might be used, and a tube would be inserted into the rectum (not far, as the sensor would be placed just before the rectum). **Laparoscopic procedure:** The sensor would be attached to the *outside* of the colon. This would be a minimally invasive surgical procedure, as it would require incisions through the skin.

concerns were raised, such as the possibility of feeling the sensor or it becoming dislodged.

- The project received advice from a steering group of healthcare experts, including gastroenterology and bowel control nursing, who provided valuable input. This group also had differing views on whether implantation should be endoscopic or laparoscopic, and raised concerns about potential risks, such as bowel damage.

A bowel phantom (simulator) was manufactured to test the sensors in a physiologically relevant environment and to reduce animal testing.

Digital interface (app) design

- Participants expressed the need for more certainty about when a movement in the bowel could happen, what was happening in the bowel, whether it was a bowel movement and/or wind, and whether there was more stool remaining in the bowel. In the app design, 'movement of the bowel' refers to both bowel movements and wind, with 'wind' meaning excessive wind.
- The research findings suggest that the following functionality could help address these needs. The app could provide alerts for an imminent bowel movement or suggest an optimal time to attempt one. It could also notify of a build-up of wind or prolonged lack of movement in the bowel. Additionally, the app could support recording and tracking movements in the bowel and relevant aspects of daily living, such as medication use. Graphical displays of historical data could help identify patterns and triggers for bowel symptoms, while graphical displays of predicted future movements in the bowel could aid planning and help prevent accidents.

- Building on the above functionality, specific features were identified, such as a push notification providing 30-minutes notice of a bowel movement and a tracking form with fields for recording movements in the bowel (e.g., 'accident' to track bowel incontinence). Privacy was highlighted as important, such as the option to choose more discreet wording for notifications. Participants felt the app could enhance their interactions with healthcare professionals.

Mock-up showing the capability to customise tracking needs, including the option to not track wind.

Mock-up showing a blank form with the (optional) measures displayed for recording soiling when passing wind.

Mock-up showing 'Bowel movement' (quantity) and 'Mucous' for 'Today'.

How the findings will be used

The findings are being shared in research reports and presentations, but no names or personal details will be included. This research adds to the growing body of knowledge on digital technologies for bowel management and could help improve implantable sensors and companion digital interfaces (e.g., apps). Due to the promising sensor testing and positive feedback, the findings are also being used to apply for funding to continue the research as well as explore how this technology could help with other health conditions.

Contact details for questions

Since it has been three years since the first Consent Form for the study was signed, we will be deleting your contact details from our records. However, if you have any questions, please feel free to contact Andrea Taylor, Glasgow School of Art via email: a.taylor@gsa.ac.uk

Thank you once again for your participation in the study!
Alex, Andrea, Gloria, Michael, and Wendy 😊